

Immune-regulating complex orchestrates protection against sepsis

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Abstract

The prognosis of sepsis, a life-threatening organ dysfunction with high mortality, is closely related to the immune function of the host. It was found that the toll-like receptor (TLR) 7/8 signaling pathway could be activated to achieve the prevention and treatment of sepsis. Herein, a kind of immune-regulating complex is constructed by simple mixing R848, a TLR 7/8 agonist, with sodium alginate (ALG). Such an immune-regulating complex (R848@ALG) could form a hydrogel *in vivo*, enabling the sustained release of R848 and thereby activating the immune system. Furthermore, the complex could enhance the function of immune cells to accelerate the clearance of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), reduce the inflammatory injury induced by various cytokines, and increase the survival rate of septic mice. Therefore, our work provides a simple and effective immune-regulating complex for preventing and treating *E. coli*-induced sepsis.

Keywords

ALG hydrogel, immune-regulating complex, sepsis protection, TLR7/8 agonist

Introduction

Sepsis is characterized as a kind of life-threatening organ dysfunction that is induced by a dysregulated host response to infection (Evans et al. 2021). Despite the significant progress in intensive care medicine, sepsis remains a leading cause of death and critical illness. In recent years, many studies have shown that immune dysfunction and immunosuppression caused by sepsis were considered to be important factors inducing death in septic patients (Hotchkiss et al. 2019; Shao et al. 2019; McBride et al. 2020; Lu et al. 2022). It has been reported that regulat-

ing the *in vivo* immune response to restore the immune homeostasis of septic patients could effectively improve the prognosis of patients in the clinic (Boomer et al. 2011; Singer et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2018; Shao et al. 2019; Zijlstra et al. 2019). Therefore, it is expected to provide effective strategies for the prevention and treatment of sepsis by using immune regulation.

The innate immune system can effectively inhibit the reproduction and diffusion of pathogens by recognizing the characteristic molecular patterns on the surface of bacteria, viruses, and other microorganisms (Gotts and Matthay 2016; Miyake et al. 2018). Toll-like receptor (TLR) is an im-

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portant member of the pattern recognition receptor family that recognizes pathogens and initiates the *in vivo* immune response (Bamigbola and Ali 2022). The TLR7/8 receptor, a typical TLR receptor, recognizes viral and bacterial nucleic acids to trigger a strong innate immune response in the host (Kawai and Akira 2006; Jian et al. 2019). It was found that TLR7-deficient mice could not activate macrophages to produce cytokines and dendritic cells to mature, leading to ineffective clearance of pathogens (Hemmi et al. 2002). Furthermore, clinical studies showed that the activation of the TLR7/8 signaling pathway could improve the anti-infective response of patients to viruses and other pathogens and reduce the pathological damage induced by sepsis, indicating an important role of the TLR7/8 signaling pathway in sepsis protection (Diebold et al. 2004; Triantafyllou et al. 2005; Pockros et al. 2007; Kawai and Akira 2010; Seo et al. 2010; Meyer et al. 2013). Therefore, regulating the TLR7/8 signaling pathway is of great significance for the prevention and treatment of sepsis.

Based on the above study, we used R848, a TLR7/8 agonist in the clinic, loaded into sodium alginate (ALG), a kind of clinical dressing, to form an immune-regulating complex, defined as R848@ALG. This complex can form an ALG hydrogel *in vivo* and achieve sustained release of R848 from the ALG hydrogel. Compared with free R848, R848@ALG could enhance the *in vivo* immune response, activate various immune cells, and significantly increase the survival rate of mice suffering from sepsis caused by *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) (Fig. 1A). Therefore, R848@ALG can be used as a kind of simple but effective immune-regulatory complex against *E. coli*-induced sepsis.

Materials and methods

Materials

RAW 264.7 cells, a kind of F4/80⁺ cell line, were cultured in DMEM medium. C57BL/6 female mice were fed under protocols approved by the Soochow University Laboratory Animal Center. ALG was obtained from J&K Chemical. R848 was purchased from Selleck. Anti-NK1.1 antibody, anti-CD45 antibody, anti-F4/80 antibody, anti-CD206 antibody, anti-CD80 antibody, anti-CD8 antibody, anti-Gr-1 antibody, and anti-CD11b antibody were purchased from BioLegend for flow cytometry. The enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits for interferon (IFN)- γ , interleukin (IL)-6, IL-1 α , IL-10, IL-23, and IL-17A were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Other unmentioned chemicals were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Characterization of ALG hydrogel

The morphology of the ALG hydrogel was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Hitachi S-4800. The TA Instrument AR 2000 stress-controlled rheometer was used to measure the dynamic rheolog-

ical behavior of the ALG hydrogel formed by a 10 mg/mL ALG solution and a 10 mg/mL calcium chloride (CaCl₂) solution.

R848 release from ALG hydrogel

The release of R848 in ALG hydrogel (10 mg/mL ALG solution) was studied in 10 mg/mL CaCl₂ solution by taking samples at specific time intervals and analyzing them using ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-VIS).

In vivo local fluorescence imaging

Female mice were subcutaneously injected with sodium alginate loaded with fluorescent dye cyanine 5.5 (Cy5.5) or free Cy5.5 to investigate the retention time of Cy5.5 using an *in vivo* fluorescence imaging system (PE Lumina).

The *in vivo* protection against *E. coli*-induced sepsis

C57BL/6 mice (6–8 weeks, female) were randomly allocated into five groups: PBS group, 7 h group, 24 h group, 48 h group, and 72 h group. For *E. coli*-induced sepsis protection assessment, at different time points after R848@ALG (3 mg/kg R848 and 19 mg/kg ALG) treatment, the mice were lethally challenged with 5×10^6 bacterial colony-forming units (CFU) of *E. coli*. The survival of all mice was monitored.

Furthermore, healthy C57BL/6 mice (6–8 weeks, female) were randomly distributed into the PBS group, ALG group, R848 group, and R848@ALG group. All mice were challenged with *E. coli* (5×10^6 CFU) at 72 h after subcutaneous injection of different formulations (3 mg/kg R848 and 19 mg/kg ALG). The survival and body weight of all mice were monitored for 4 days.

In vivo analysis of bacterial clearance and immunophenotype

The C57BL/6J female mice were first distributed in the PBS group, ALG group, R848 group, and R848@ALG group. All the mice were intraperitoneally injected with *E. coli* (3×10^6 CFU) at 72 h after subcutaneous injection of various treatments (3 mg/kg R848 and 19 mg/kg ALG). At 6 h post *E. coli* injection, the blood and lung tissues from all the infected mice were acquired, homogenized, and measured for bacterial counts on LB agar plates. At 18 h post *E. coli* (5×10^6 CFU) injection, the heart, liver, spleen, lung, kidney, and intestine from the infected mice were collected and stained with Hematoxylin Eosin (H&E) to observe pathological changes.

Furthermore, the changes of NK cells (NK1.1⁺) in CD45⁺ cells, CD80⁺ cells in F4/80⁺ cells, CD8⁺ cells in CD45⁺ cells, CD206⁺ cells in F4/80⁺ cells, and neutrophils (Gr1⁺) in CD11b⁺ cells in blood and peritoneal lavage fluids were evaluated by flow cytometry at 6 h post bacterial infection. The concentrations of various cytokines in serum before and after *E. coli* infection were detected by ELISA assay.

In vitro *E. coli* uptake

E. coli was cultured and collected for labeling with the fluorescent dye Cy5.5. The collected *E. coli* was first heat-killed for 30 minutes at 95 °C. The heat-killed *E. coli* was then labeled with Cy5.5 (*E. coli*-Cy5.5). The RAW 264.7 cells cultured in 24-well plates were incubated with PBS, ALG, R848, and R848@ALG (0.3 mg/mL R848 and 1.9 mg/mL ALG) for 6 h. The treated cells were incubated with *E. coli*-Cy5.5 at 37 °C for 30 minutes (the ratio of RAW 264.7 cell/*E. coli* = 1/20). The *E. coli* uptake in RAW 264.7 cells was detected by flow cytometry and confocal fluorescence microscopy. Furthermore, the bacterial colonies in the treated cells were evaluated on LB agar plates.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were assessed using GraphPad Prism software version 6 (GraphPad Software Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Differences in survival were calculated using the log-rank test. All data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. The statistical significance for three or more groups was compared using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's post-hoc analysis.

Results and discussion

As a kind of linear polyanionic polysaccharide, ALG is composed of two structural units, mannuronic acid and guluronic acid, which is widely used in tissue and cell engineering (Pawar and Edgar 2012; Chen et al. 2019). Under mild physiological conditions, ALG solution can react with multivalent cations, such as calcium ions (Ca^{2+}), to form a hydrogel with a three-dimensional network structure, which is suitable to deliver various water-soluble molecules (West et al. 2007). The ALG hydrogel was synthesized by the combination of ALG solution and calcium chloride (CaCl_2) solution. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images revealed that the ALG hydrogel exhibited a porous network structure (Fig. 1B). It was found in rheological analysis that the ALG hydrogel was formed when the CaCl_2 solution was added (Fig. 1C). R848, a kind of TLR7/8 agonist, was simply mixed with ALG to form the immunostimulatory complex (R848@ALG). The release profile of R848 was then studied in the ALG hydrogel (Fig. 1D). The result indicated that R848 was sustainably released from the ALG hydrogel.

To study whether the retention of R848 in the ALG hydrogel is prolonged *in vivo*, the fluorescent dye cyanine 5.5 (Cy5.5), a surrogate for the free drug, was utilized to mimic the *in vivo* retention behavior of the drug loaded

Figure 1. Sepsis protection and the characterization of an immune-stimulating composite. **A.** The scheme illustrating the mechanism of R848@ALG to achieve effective protection against *E. coli*-induced sepsis by a single subcutaneous injection of R848@ALG. **B.** Representative SEM image of the ALG hydrogel. **C.** Evolution of the elastic (G') and viscous (G'') over time for the ALG hydrogel. **D.** Cumulative release profile of R848 from the ALG hydrogel.

into the ALG hydrogel (Fig. 2A). A subcutaneous administration of free Cy5.5 or Cy5.5 mixed with ALG solution (Cy5.5@ALG) was given to healthy mice. As illustrated in Fig. 2B, C, it was found that Cy5.5 in the ALG hydrogel could be retained *in vivo* for about 240 h, while free Cy5.5 could be retained *in vivo* for only 97 h. These results of fluorescence imaging indicated that the ALG hydrogel can enhance the retention of the free drug *in vivo*.

Encouraged by the results of prolonged release and *in vivo* retention of small molecules in the ALG hydrogel, the protective effect of the R848@ALG complex was studied

in vivo (Fig. 2D). PBS or R848@ALG (3 mg/kg R848 and 19 mg/kg ALG) was administered subcutaneously to mice in the PBS group and the R848@ALG group. At the indicated time points after injection, a lethal dose of *E. coli* (5×10^6 CFU) was administered to all the mice. As shown in Fig. 2E, all the PBS-treated mice died within 25 h. Furthermore, the R848@ALG-treated mice could reach 20% for 7 h injection, 80% for 24 h injection, 60% for 48 h injection, and 100% for 72 h injection (Fig. 2E), respectively. This result proved that sepsis protection induced by the R848@ALG complex could be improved with the prolonged time of treatment.

Figure 2. *In vivo* protective effect against *E. coli*-induced sepsis. **A**, Schematic illustration to exhibit the enhanced retention induced by the ALG hydrogel *in vivo*. **B**, **C**, *In vivo* fluorescence imaging photos (**B**) and quantification (**C**) of the release profiles of free Cy5.5 and Cy5.5 encapsulated with the ALG hydrogel (Cy5.5@ALG). **D**, Schematic illustration to exhibit the protection of R848@ALG at different time points in *E. coli*-induced sepsis. **E**, Survival rates of mice challenged by *E. coli*-induced sepsis ($n = 5$ per group) at different time points after R848@ALG subcutaneous injection. **F**, Schematic illustration to show the protection of various treatments after 72 h in *E. coli*-induced sepsis. **G**, **H**, Survival rates (**G**) and body weights (**H**) of mice 72 h post different treatments challenged by *E. coli*-induced sepsis ($n = 8$ per group). Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Survival curves were compared by log-rank test.

Based on the efficiency of sepsis protection induced by R848@ALG, we selected 72 h post subcutaneous injection to evaluate the *in vivo* anti-infective effect of the R848@ALG complex. Firstly, the mice were distributed into the PBS group, ALG group, R848 group, and R848@ALG group and subcutaneously injected with the corresponding formulation (3 mg/kg R848 and 19 mg/kg ALG). The mice received a lethal injection of *E. coli* (5×10^6 CFU) at 72 h after the subcutaneous injection (Fig. 2F). It is found in Fig. 2G that the R848@ALG-treated mice could reach 84.6% survival compared with 0% for the PBS-treated group, 0% for the ALG-treated group, and 25% for the

R848-treated group. In addition, relatively stable body weight was observed in the surviving mice during the sepsis challenge (Fig. 2H).

Immunomodulators can promote bacterial clearance and alleviate tissue injury induced by sepsis (Ghelani et al. 2022; Achmad et al. 2024; Li et al. 2026). Therefore, the *in vivo* organ protection induced by the R848@ALG complex was subsequently evaluated (Fig. 3A). As depicted in Fig. 3B–E, the bacterial counts in the blood (Fig. 3B, C) and lung tissue (Fig. 3D, E) of the R848@ALG-treated group were significantly lower than those in the PBS-treated group at 6 h post *E. coli* infection, indicating that the

Figure 3. The *in vivo* protective effect against *E. coli* infection induced by R848@ALG. (A) Schematic illustration to evaluate the protective effect against *E. coli*-induced sepsis after different treatments. B, C. Representative images (B) and statistical data (C) of *E. coli* colonization in the blood of mice at 6 h after *E. coli* infection. D, E. Representative images (D) and statistical data (E) of *E. coli* colonization in the lung tissue of mice at 6 h after *E. coli* infection. F. H&E staining images of the major organs of mice at 18 h after *E. coli*-induced sepsis. Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Statistical significance was calculated by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test.

R848@ALG complex can improve bacterial clearance *in vivo*. Furthermore, to evaluate the histology of the organs, H&E staining was used for analysis at 18 h after bacterial infection. As exhibited in Fig. 3F, the damage and inflammation in the R848@ALG group were lower than in the other group, suggesting that R848@ALG treatment can improve the prognosis of septic mice.

Thereafter, the mechanism of the R848@ALG complex in sepsis protection was studied *in vivo* (Fig. 4A). The changes of various immune cells were evaluated before or after sepsis challenge by *E. coli* (3×10^6 CFU) (Fig. 4A). Fig. 4B–E showed that the R848@ALG-treated mice had significantly higher percentages of NK cells and CD8⁺ T cells in the blood, while the percentages of CD80⁺F4/80⁺ cells and neutrophils were significantly decreased. However, there was no significant change in the percent of CD206⁺F4/80⁺ cells in the two groups (Suppl. material 1: fig. S1). Furthermore, the percentages of NK cells, CD80⁺F4/80⁺ cells, and CD206⁺F4/80⁺ cells in blood were obviously elevated in the R848@ALG group when the mice were challenged by sepsis (Fig. 4F–H). The percentages of CD8⁺ T cells and neutrophils were not sig-

nificantly changed post sepsis challenge (Suppl. material 1: fig. S2A, B). Furthermore, R848@ALG-treated mice showed an increased percent of NK cells in the abdominal cavity infection (Fig. 4I). However, the percentages of CD80⁺F4/80⁺ cells, CD206⁺F4/80⁺ cells, and neutrophils at the infectious site did not change significantly (Suppl. material 1: fig. S3A–C). NK cells are vital immune cells that play a crucial role in anti-infective immunity during sepsis (Zhang et al. 2019; Luo et al. 2025). It has been reported that the quantity and proportion of NK cells are negatively correlated with the mortality rate of patients with sepsis (Feng et al. 2020).

Inflammatory cytokines play an important role in the pathogenesis of sepsis and are a defining hallmark of the systemic inflammatory response (Wang et al. 2025). During the progress of sepsis, a balanced inflammatory response is beneficial to the host. However, excessive activation of inflammation results in uncontrolled cytokine production, which aggravates inflammatory cell infiltration and tissue damage, triggers multiple organ dysfunction, and may ultimately lead to organ failure and death (Muhar et al. 2023). Therefore, the levels of various cytokines in serum were

Figure 4. The *in vivo* changes of immune phenotype induced by R848@ALG. A. Schematic illustration to evaluate the changes of immune cells in mice with different treatments before or after *E. coli*-induced sepsis challenge. B–E. The percentages of NK cells (NK1.1⁺) in CD45⁺ cells (B), CD80⁺ cells in F4/80⁺ cells (C), CD8⁺ cells in CD45⁺ cells (D), and neutrophils (Gr1⁺) in CD11b⁺ cells (E) in the blood of mice at 72 h after different treatments ($n = 4$ per group). F–I. The percentages of NK cells (NK1.1⁺) in CD45⁺ cells (F), CD80⁺ cells in F4/80⁺ cells (G), CD206⁺ cells in F4/80⁺ cells (H) in blood, and NK cells (NK1.1⁺) in CD45⁺ cells (I) in peritoneal lavage fluid of mice from the groups at 6 h after *E. coli* challenge ($n = 4$ per group). Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Statistical significance was calculated by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test.

evaluated (Fig. 5A). As exhibited in Fig. 5B–G, no marked difference was observed in the levels of cytokines IFN- γ , IL-6, IL-1 α , IL-10, IL-23, and IL-17A between the PBS-treated and R848@ALG-treated mice, indicating the *in vivo* safety of the R848@ALG complex. However, the cytokines in sera, involving IFN- γ , IL-6, IL-1 α , IL-10, and IL-23, were significantly down-regulated in R848@ALG-treated and R848-treated mice after the sepsis challenge, implying that R848@ALG could decrease the level of cytokines by enhanced bacterial clearance *in vivo*. These results indicated that the R848@ALG complex could enhance the immune cell function *in vivo*, thereby achieving bacterial clearance and providing protection against sepsis.

Based on the protective role of NK cells and F4/80⁺ cells in sepsis *in vivo*, RAW 264.7 cells, a type of mouse F4/80⁺ cells, were used to explore the *in vitro* function of the R848@ALG complex (Fig. 6A). RAW 264.7 cells were pretreated with PBS, ALG, R848, or R848@ALG for 6 h first. Subsequently, the bacterial uptake of these cells was measured by using Cy5.5-labeled *E. coli* (*E. coli*-Cy5.5). As shown in Fig. 6B–D, R848@ALG and R848 could enhance the *E. coli* uptake of RAW 264.7 cells. Furthermore, it was found that R848@ALG and R848 treatment could enhance the bactericidal capability of RAW 264.7 cells (Fig. S4A, B). These results exhibited that the anti-infective ability of R848@ALG-treated RAW 264.7 cells was enhanced by improving bacterial uptake.

Conclusion

In this study, a kind of immune-regulating complex (R848@ALG) was prepared by mixing R848, a TLR 7/8 agonist, with ALG solution against *E. coli*-induced sepsis. This immune-regulating complex could form a hydrogel *in vivo* and improve the *in vivo* immune function of R848 by sustained release of R848. Furthermore, the complex could activate *in vivo* various immune cells, including NK cells and F4/80⁺ cells, to enhance immune responses, accelerate bacterial clearance in organs and blood, decrease inflammatory injury induced by cytokines, and finally improve the survival rate of mice challenged by sepsis. Meanwhile, the complex could increase bacterial uptake of F4/80⁺ cells to kill *E. coli* effectively *in vitro*. Therefore, this immune-regulatory complex could be used as a simple but effective immunomodulator to provide a potential therapeutic method for sepsis prevention and treatment. This study presents a translatable, safe, and highly effective immunoregulatory therapeutic strategy for *E. coli*-induced sepsis that may improve administration efficiency, prolong therapeutic efficacy, and enhance organ protection in sepsis treatment. The ALG hydrogel-based sustained-release system represents a versatile platform with broad potential for delivering a range of anti-infective and immunomodulatory agents. However, this study has several limitations. The *in vivo* experiments were conducted

Figure 5. The *in vivo* concentrations of various cytokines induced by R848@ALG. **A.** Schematic illustration to evaluate the levels of cytokines in mice with different treatments before or after bacterial challenge. **B–G.** Cytokine levels, including IFN- γ , IL-6, IL-1 α , IL-10, IL-23, and IL-17A, in sera from pretreated mice before or at 6 h after *E. coli* challenge ($n = 4$ per group). Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Statistical significance was calculated by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test.

Figure 6. The *in vitro* bacterial uptake of macrophages enhanced by R848@ALG. **A.** Schematic illustration to evaluate the bacterial uptake of macrophages pretreated by different formulations. **B, C.** Representative flow cytometry data (**B**) and statistical data (**C**) of the uptake of Cy5.5 fluorescent dye-labeled *E. coli* (*E. coli*-Cy5.5) in RAW 264.7 cells after incubation with different treatments for 6 h. MFI means mean fluorescence intensity. **D.** Confocal fluorescence microscopy images to exhibit the *E. coli*-Cy5.5 uptake of RAW 264.7 cells pretreated with various formulations for 6 h. Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Statistical significance was calculated by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test.

only in mice in this study, and further validation in rats or larger animal models is still required. Furthermore, the optimal dosage of the R848@ALG immunomodulator has not yet been systematically evaluated. The safety profile of R848@ALG remains to be further evaluated in the future.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: SYXK (苏) 2022-0043

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: RAW 264.7 cells ATCC TIB-71.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

He Zhao and Jian Wang; methodology, Xinxian Guan, Xinjing Lv and Shengling Yu; software, Guiyong Fan; validation, Jie Min,

Yongrui Song and Wenqian Zhao; formal analysis, Lin Liu; investigation, Min Zhang; data curation, Xinxian Guan; writing – original draft preparation, Xinxian Guan; writing – review and editing, He Zhao; visualization, Jie Huang; supervision, Jian Wang; project administration, Jie Huang; funding acquisition, He Zhao and Jian Wang. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary figures

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